

Dendrochronological analysis of timber from three shipwrecks, wrecks 2, 5 and 6, found in Varberg, Sweden

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Fourteen samples from three shipwrecks found during excavations in Varberg, Sweden, were submitted for dendrochronological analysis, to determine their date and provenance. A budget for analysis of six samples in total was available, so the most dendrochronologically suitable samples were selected for analysis. However, in order to attain the best possible outcome, six samples from wreck 2, two samples from wreck 5 and two samples from wreck 6 have been analysed.

The results of these analyses are described in this report.

Fig. 1. Bar diagram illustrating the dendrochronological dating of the oak samples from Varberg ships 2 and 5. (analysis and illustration: Aoife Daly).

Chronology

Varberg 2 – dating

Nine samples are from wreck 2. Six samples are analysed dendrochronologically, from three frames and from three planks, and all six are dated. They are all oak (*Quercus* sp.).

As mentioned above, three samples were not analysed from Varberg 2. A sample from frame 1210 contains c. 45 tree rings and is not therefore suitable for analysis. The sample from plank 1215 contains 60-70 rings, and the sample is broken into three parts, so this sample was not prioritised. The sample from plank 1236 contains c. 62 rings including sapwood, but it is taken at a knotty part of the plank, so it was not prioritised.

The three planks that were analysed all contain only heartwood and they are all tangentially converted from the parent tree. Plank 1239 contains 140 tree rings, and its tree-ring curve covers the period AD 1374-1513. Allowing for the missing sapwood, the felling of the tree that this plank was made from can be placed at after AD 1523.

Plank 1213 is preserved to the heartwood/sapwood boundary, and it contains 110 tree rings. Its tree-ring curve covers the period AD 1408-1517 and it is from a tree felled in the range AD 1527-42.

		Z3770019 1201	Z377006a 1234	Z3770029 1204	Z3770039 1205	Z377004a 1239	Z377005a 1213	Z378001_1 1283	Z378002a 1288
wreck 2 Z377M002	Z3770019 1201	*	2.82	3.69	3.93	3.69	3.06	0.18	-
	Z377006a 1234	2.82	*	4.12	2.83	3.56	2.26	2.56	\
	Z3770029 1204	3.69	4.12	*	4.05	3.82	2.08	-	\
	Z3770039 1205	3.93	2.83	4.05	*	5.15	1.70	-	0.24
	Z377004a 1239	3.69	3.56	3.82	5.15	*	3.66	-	\
	Z377005a 1213	3.06	2.26	2.08	1.70	3.66	*	0.09	\
Wreck 5 Z378M001	Z378001_1 1283	0.18	2.56	-	-	-	0.09	*	7.25
	Z378002a 1288	-	\	\	0.24	\	\	7.25	*

Table 1. Varberg ships 2 and 5, Sweden. Matrix of correlation, each dated sample with each other.

Plank 1234 has 89 heartwood rings and is possibly preserved to the heartwood/sapwood boundary, but this could not be confirmed anatomically. The tree-ring curve from this plank covers the period AD 1425-1513 and if the heartwood/sapwood boundary is present, the plank is from a tree felled in the range AD 1523-38.

The samples from the three analysed frames all have sapwood preserved and one also has bark edge. Frame 1201 contains 102 tree rings, of which 19 are sapwood rings and this sample has bark edge preserved. It was however not possible to determine the season of felling. The tree-ring curve covers the period AD 1430-1531 and this sample is from a tree felled in AD 1531-32.

Frame 1204 contains 101 tree rings, of which six are sapwood rings. This sample covers the period AD 1423-1523 and is from a tree felled in the range AD 1527-42. Frame 1205 has 163 tree rings including 14 sapwood rings. This frame is from a tree felled in the range AD 1531-41.

Taking the dating results as a whole, and assuming that all timbers are from the building phase of the ship, we might place the date of that felling in AD 1531-32 (fig. 1).

Varberg 5 – dating

Two samples are from Varberg wreck 5 and, as mentioned above, both samples were analysed. Both these samples are oak (*Quercus* sp.), and both are dated.

Both samples are from tangentially converted planks and both have only heartwood preserved. Plank 1283 contains 99 tree rings, and its tree-ring curve covers the period AD 1499-1597. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling of the tree that was used to make this plank can be placed at after AD1608.

Plank 1288 contains 56 tree rings all heartwood. Initially, it was suspected that the heartwood/sapwood boundary was present on the sample, but it is possible that the softer outer edge is from deterioration of the wood. The tree-ring curve from plank 1288 covers the period AD 1511-1566 and the felling of the tree that was used to make the plank can be placed at after AD 1576.

If both planks are from the building phase of Varberg 5, we can place the date of the felling of these trees at after 1608 (see fig. 1).

Varberg 6 – dating

Two samples are from Varberg 6. They are oak (*Quercus* sp.) and both were analysed. Keel 1306 contains 108 tree rings, and is possibly preserved to the heartwood/sapwood boundary. Frame 1297 has 110 tree rings, including 17 sapwood rings. Unfortunately it has not been possible to find a dating position for these two samples.

Filename	start year-end year	Z377M002 AD1368- AD1531	site name
<i>Master and site chronologies</i>			
4077M001	AD1310-AD1540	11.29	Nyborg slot (Daly 1999)
2x900001	AD830-AD1997	8.62	Sjælland Denmark 227 timbers (Nationalmuseet)
SScanM25	AD1343-AD1548	8.57	Southern Scandinavia 36 timbers (Daly unpubl)
B027oak C o...	AD1331-AD1557	8.47	Gammel Strand Copenhagen C orange 23 timbers (Daly 2016)
WSwedM25	AD1344-AD1560	8.47	West Sweden 49 timbers (Daly unpubl)
8111M001	AD1350-AD1480	8.28	Astrup K. 13 timbers (Daly 1998a)
ZEALAND9	AD452-AD1997	8.26	Sjælland Denmark 476 timbers (Daly unpubl)
DCCDnorw	AD1248-AD1648	8.19	Norway 192 timbers (Daly et al unpubl DCCD)
81M00004	AD1350-AD1480	8.04	kirker i Vendsyssel W Sweden group 24 timber (Daly 1998b)
H039M001	AD1344-AD1597	7.94	Aalborg ved Stranden mfl group 1 29 timbers (Daly 2022)
SE08M001	AD1348-AD1517	7.5	Uddevalla 191 1 SU Trappan 4 timbers (Daly 2018)
8127M001	AD846-AD1771	7.38	Ålborg Østerå & Boulevarden 67 timbers (Daly 2000 2001a)
SM000005	AD1274-AD1974	7.36	Skåne Blekinge (Lund University)
30800009	AD1301-AD1561	7.23	Halmstad Sweden (Bartholin pers comm)
B027oak B p...	AD1248-AD1532	7.12	Gammel Strand Copenhagen B purple 21 timbers (Daly 2016)
2121M002	AD1052-AD1596	7.02	Suså Næstved all posts (Daly 2001b)
<i>Chronologies from ships</i>			
Z253M001	AD1339-AD1566	9.21	Bispevika 18 Oslo 2 timbers (Daly 2019)
Z160M005_6_...	AD1317-AD1557	9.04	Bispevika 8 big 15 timbers (Daly 2023b)
Z178M001	AD1406-AD1510	8.01	Bispevika 15 ship Oslo 3 timbers (Daly 2017)
Z110M001	AD1342-AD1601	7.97	Barcode ship 3 BC03 Oslo 4 timbers (Daly 2013)
WSshipsM01	AD1352-AD1636	7.57	West Swedish ships 29 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Z0923M03	AD1328-AD1618	7.33	Vasa group 3 31 timbers (Daly 2021)
Z109M001	AD1437-AD1597	7.12	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo 4 timbers (Daly 2013)
Z249M001	AD1375-AD1588	7.00	Bispevika 16 Oslo 2 timbers (Daly 2019)

Table 2. Varberg ship 2, Sweden. Result of the correlation between the average for Varberg 2 (Z377M002) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Provenance

The tree-ring curves from the dated samples are compared with each other, and the correlations are shown in table 1. Samples from Varberg 2 are highlighted in blue (planks dark blue, frames light blue), those from Varberg 5 are in yellow. Correlations values (t -value) between the samples from Varberg 2 show significant similarity, indicating that the trees for this ship came from broadly the same region. The two samples from Varberg 5 match highly-significantly with each other. There is no significant correlation between wreck 2 and 5, but the overlap between these two is short (only 33 years).

Varberg 2 – provenance

An average of all six dated samples from Varberg 2 is made (Z377M002). It is 164 years long, and covers the period AD 1368-1531. The correlations between this average and diverse tree-ring datasets for Northern Europe are shown in table 2. The average for the Varberg 2 wreck is dating against a

large range of southern Scandinavian tree-ring datasets, with high t -values appearing with Danish and western Swedish site and master chronologies. Extensive movement of timber as a raw material across the Øresund within the territory of 16th century Denmark took place in the past (see e.g. Daly 2024), so many of the chronologies for Denmark that Varberg 2 correlates with derive from timber that came from the Swedish side of the Øresund/Kattegat. Varberg 2 is therefore probably built of oak timber that grew in western Sweden.

Varberg 2 is also picking up significant correlation with a range of shipwrecks from Oslo, that have, through dendrochronology, also been shown to be of west-swedish oak (Daly 2017, 2019, 2023b, see table 2).

Filename	start year-end year	Z378M001 AD1499- AD1597	site name
<i>Master and site chronologies</i>			
SM000012	AD1125-AD1720	5.83	Sverige Vest (Bråthen 1982)
F009M001	AD1359-AD1623	5.53	Hobro two datasets 8 timbers (Daly 2007)
2121M002	AD1052-AD1596	5.36	Suså Næstved all posts (Daly 2001b)
CD60IZ01	AD1450-AD1635	5.21	Ryomgård 9 timbers (Nationalmuseet revised Daly 2007)
ZEALAND9	AD452-AD1997	5.15	Sjælland Denmark 476 timbers (Daly unpubl)
<i>Chronologies from ships</i>			
Z323M002	AD1436-AD1626	5.39	Vaxholm wreck 3 gr2 2 timbers (Daly 2023a)
Z0923M02	AD1330-AD1625	5.12	Vasa group 2 strong 47 timbers (Daly 2021)

Table 3. Varberg ship 5, Sweden. Result of the correlation between the average for Varberg 5 (Z378M001) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Varberg 5 – provenance

As mentioned above, the tree-ring curves from the two Varberg 5 samples match each other, and these are averaged to a mean, Z378M001. This average is 99 years long and covers the period AD 1499-1597. The correlations that this average give against diverse northern European tree-ring datasets is shown in table 3. This ship achieves highest correlations with west Sweden and with diverse Danish sites. From just two samples we can suggest that the trees for this ship grew on the Swedish side of Øresund/Kattegat. Varberg 5 is also correlating with chronologies from the warship *Vasa* (group 2) (Daly 2021), and a similar dataset from the sister ship to *Vasa* – *Äpplet* (Vaxholm 3, group 2) (Daly 2023a).

Varberg 6 – provenance

As no dating position has been found for the two samples from Varberg 6, no provenance can be determined.

Methodology

Measuring and analysis of the material is carried out using the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) in which the calculation of the t -value (" t -test") "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is embedded. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are consulted.

A sapwood average of c. 10-25 sapwood rings is used for estimating the felling date of the two dated ships. This is a combination of the estimate for Northern Germany (ca. 20 sapwood years (-5+10) (Hollstein 1980)) and for Norway (c. 15 sapwood years (-8+6)) (Christensen & Havemann 1998).

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Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	genus	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
samples, Varberg wreck 2												
Z3770019	Varberg Tunnel wreck 2 1201 frame	102	AD1430	AD1531	C	19	Y	S	N	QUSP	0.94	AD1531-32
Z3770029	Varberg Tunnel wreck 2 1204 frame	101	AD1423	AD1523	C	6	N	S	S1	QUSP	1.52	AD1527-42
Z3770039	Varberg Tunnel wreck 2 1205 frame	163	AD1368	AD1530	C	14	N	S	S1	QUSP	0.81	AD1531-41
Z377004a	Varberg Tunnel wreck 2 1239 plank	140	AD1374	AD1513	F	0	N	T	N	QUSP	0.99	after AD1523
Z377005a	Varberg Tunnel wreck 2 1213 plank	110	AD1408	AD1517	F	H/S	N	T	N	QUSP	1.53	AD1527-42
Z377006a	Varberg Tunnel wreck 2 1234 plank	89	AD1425	AD1513	F	H/S?	N	T	N	QUSP	1.46	AD1523-38?
	Varberg Tunnel wreck 2 1210 frame	c. 45								QUSP		not measured
	Varberg Tunnel wreck 2 1215 plank	60-70						T		QUSP		not measured
	Varberg Tunnel wreck 2 1236 plank	c. 62						T		QUSP		not measured
Average, Varberg wreck 2												
Z377M002	Varberg 2 6 timbers	164	AD1368	AD1531						QUSP	1.12	average
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus</i> sp., oak. PISY = <i>Pinus</i> sp., pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix</i> sp., spruce/larch. ABAL = <i>Abies</i> sp., fir. FASY = <i>Fagus</i> sp., beech												
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.			10 August 2024									

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	genus	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Samples, Varberg wreck 5												
Z378001_1	Varberg Tunnel wreck 5 1283 plank	99	AD1499	AD1597	F	0	N	T	H1	QUSP	1.81	after AD1608
Z378002a	Varberg Tunnel wreck 5 1288 plank	56	AD1511	AD1566	G	H/S?	N	T	N	QUSP	2.63	after AD1576
Average, Varberg wreck 5												
Z378M001	Varberg Tunnel wreck 5 2 timbers	99	AD1499	AD1597						QUSP	2.01	average
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus</i> sp., oak. PISY = <i>Pinus</i> sp., pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix</i> sp., spruce/larch. ABAL = <i>Abies</i> sp., fir. FASY = <i>Fagus</i> sp., beech												
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.							10 August 2024					

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	genus	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
samples, Varberg wreck 6												
Z3790019	Varberg Tunnel wreck 6 1306 keel	108			G	H/S?	N	O	H1	QUSP	1.95	undated
Z379002a	Varberg Tunnel wreck 6 1297 frame	110			G	17	N	O	S1	QUSP	0.95	undated
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus</i> sp., oak. PISY = <i>Pinus</i> sp., pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix</i> sp., spruce/larch. ABAL = <i>Abies</i> sp., fir. FASY = <i>Fagus</i> sp., beech												
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